

Studies on Synergistic Effects of Drip Fertigation and Pruning techniques on Cotton Growth and physiological characters of ELS cotton CO14

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Abstract

The conventional approach to cotton cultivation in India faces significant challenges attributed to climate change, erratic rainfall distribution and the crop's extended growth cycle. These circumstances underscore the need to consider alternative methods such as pruning in cotton as viable solutions to overcome these challenges. This approach not only offers potential solutions but also opens avenues for further exploration in cotton farming practices. This study aimed to determine effect of the drip fertigation and pruning techniques on growth and physiological parameters of ELS cotton CO14. The experiment was conducted using a split plot design with three replications. The main plots were allocated to different fertigation treatments: M₁-75% NPK, M₂-100% NPK, M₃-125% NPK, and M₄-STCR (soil test crop response) based fertilizer application. Within each main plot, subplot treatments consisted of different pruning techniques: S₁-15 cm, S₂-30 cm, and S₃-45 cm. The results indicated significant effects of varied NPK fertigation rates and pruning techniques on various growth parameters. Specifically, plants subjected to 125% NPK fertigation showed increased plant height at 66.85 cm & 76.30 cm, dry matter production at 1.24 t ha⁻¹ & 2.55 t ha⁻¹, leaf area index at 1.69 & 2.23, chlorophyll content at 42.07 & 46.33, AGR at 2.63 g d⁻¹ & 2.37 g d⁻¹ and CGR at 3.22 g m⁻² d⁻¹ & 4.41 g m⁻² d⁻¹ by

60 days after sowing (DAS) in main crop and pruned crop. Concerning pruning techniques, cotton pruned at S₃-45cm height exhibited significantly higher plant height at 76.20 cm, DMP at 2.38 t ha⁻¹, LAI at 2.03, chlorophyll content at 43.92, AGR at 2.19 g d⁻¹ and CGR at 4.07 g m⁻² d⁻¹.

Key words: Pruning, Fertigation, Growth and physiological characters

Introduction

Cotton, known as the "King of fiber" and "White gold," is a natural fiber of immense global significance. China, India, and the USA are the leading producers of cotton. Cotton is widely grown across tropical and subtropical regions spanning more than seventy countries worldwide. In India, cotton holds deep cultural roots and plays a pivotal role in the agricultural economy. Employing approximately 70 million people, it contributes nearly 75% of the raw material used in India's textile industry (Ushanandini et al., 2017). India stands a unique position as the only country cultivating all four cultivated species of cotton and their hybrids across diverse agro-climatic conditions. Although a perennial crop with an indeterminate growth pattern and a complex taproot system influenced by various physicochemical and environmental factors, cotton is typically grown as an annual crop (Zang et al., 2020). Globally, cotton is a crucial agricultural commodity, supplying raw materials for a wide range of industrial and domestic purposes (Radhakrishnan, 2017).

As Indian agriculture transitions from the era of the Green Revolution's focus on enhancing crop productivity, there is a growing emphasis on efficient resource utilization and conservation to meet contemporary challenges (Madagoudra et al., 2023). Cotton, known for its high and sustainable productivity, heavily relies on balanced soil nutrition throughout its growth cycle. Effective nutrient supplementation, applied at the right time and in appropriate quantities, plays a crucial role in promoting cotton growth. Split applications during critical growth stages are particularly beneficial, enhancing the assimilation of photosynthates and thereby boosting crop growth rate (CGR) and leaf area, as reported by Hallikeri *et al.* (2010).

Applying fertilizers through drip fertigation is highly effective in enhancing crop yield by delivering nutrients directly through irrigation water. This method improves nutrient availability crucial for growth and development compared to conventional application techniques. Drip fertigation allows for precise and controlled delivery of fertilizers in multiple split doses, ensuring a continuous and balanced supply of nutrients directly to the root zone. This also minimizes nutrient losses in the soil due to leaching, fixation and volatilization, thereby optimizing nutrient efficiency. Moreover, drip fertigation reduces labor costs associated with fertilizer application, making it a more efficient and cost-effective approach for enhancing agricultural productivity (Singh and Bhati, 2018).

The static nature of cotton cultivation in India is primarily influenced by changing climate patterns, erratic rainfall distribution and the crop's lengthy growth period. Additionally, cotton cultivation area is limited during the rabi season due to reduced soil moisture availability. Addressing these challenges presents an opportunity to explore the pruning/ ratooning of cotton, particularly to assess growth and physiology under irrigated conditions with limited water resources. Pruning offers the potential to reduce crop duration effectively, streamline land preparation activities and minimize labor and cultivation costs. This approach not only offers potential solutions but also opens avenues for further exploration in cotton farming practices (Zhou, 2016).

The objective of the current study was to evaluate the impact of fertigation and pruning techniques on the growth and physiological characters of both the main crop and the pruned crop.

Materials and Methods:

In winter 2021 and summer 2022 the field investigation was carried in farmer's field located in Nallur village, Bhavanisagar block, Erode district, Tamil Nadu, India. The geographic coordinates of the experimental site are 11.35°N latitude, 77.168°E longitude and an altitude of 312 meters above mean sea level, falling within western agro climatic zone. The soil at experimental field was classified as calcareous clay loam, with a pH of 7.85, low available N (196 kg ha⁻¹), medium P (12 kg ha⁻¹), and high K (593 kg ha⁻¹). The study was laid out in a split plot design with three replications. The main plot consisted of fertigation treatments, while

pruning techniques were assigned to the subplot. The gross and net plot sizes were 6.3 m x 6.0 m and 4.5 m x 4.8 m, respectively. Cotton variety CO14 was grown with a spacing of 90 × 60 cm, considered as the main crop. The main crop was pruned using garden secateurs at three different heights from ground level after third picking and considered as pruned crop. Subsequently, weak and desiccated shoots were removed from the pruned stumps, followed by earthing up of plants.

Fertigation treatments in the main plot included M₁-75% NPK, M₂-100% NPK, M₃-125% NPK, and M₄-STCR (soil test crop response) based fertilizer application, while pruning techniques in the subplot comprised S₁-15 cm, S₂-30 cm, and S₃-45 cm. Drip lines equipped with in-line drippers spaced at 45 cm intervals, delivering 4 LPH, were utilized. Irrigation scheduling was set at 1.0 IW/CPE under drip fertigation, with irrigation administered once every four days. Fertigation was carried out through a venturi injector to specific to each plot. The fertilizer solution was prepared and stored in plastic containers connected to venturi. Fertigation was administered according to the prescribed schedule for cotton at each irrigation. The recommended dose of fertilizer (RDF) 150:60:60 NPK kg ha⁻¹ was applied, with nitrogen(N), phosphorus(P), and potassium(K) supplied in the form of commercial fertilizers such as urea, DAP, and muriate of potash, respectively, for the main crop. Additionally, after pruning, 25% of nitrogen alone was applied to each fertigation treatment. For STCR treatment, fertigation was administered at a rate of 134:30:30 NPK kg ha⁻¹. Biometric observations on growth and physiological characters was taken on squaring stage for main crop (60 days after sowing) and pruned crop (60 days after pruning).

The data were statistically analyzed and discussed below. For the main crop, statistical analysis focused solely on the main plot treatments (fertigation), as subplot treatments (pruning techniques) were applied after the harvest of the main crop. Conversely, for the pruned crop, statistical analysis encompassed both main plot (fertigation) and subplot (pruning techniques) treatments. This comprehensive approach enabled a thorough examination of the effects of both fertigation and pruning on the growth and physiological parameters of the pruned cotton plants. Detailed discussions and interpretations of the statistical findings of pooled means of two year data's are provided below, elucidating the impact of these treatments on crop performance and productivity.

Results and Discussion

Growth parameters

The study investigated the impact of fertigation and pruning methods on plant height, as detailed in Table 1. Pruning techniques and interaction had significant effect on plant height in pruned crop. However, the statistical analysis indicated that fertigation level in main crop plant height remained unaffected statistically. Notably, the main crop under 125% fertigation exhibited the tallest plants at 66.85 cm by 60 days after sowing (DAS). In contrast, pruned crops with the same fertigation level reached a significantly higher height of 76.30 cm at 60 days after pruning (DAP), outperforming both main crop and pruned crop under 100% fertigation (61.97 cm and 70.38 cm, respectively). The lowest plant height was recorded in STCR-based fertigation in both main crop (58.71 cm) and pruned crop (65.63 cm). This is because of continuous nutrient availability and more nutrient uptake during their critical growth periods of cotton. With respect to pruning techniques, cotton pruned at 45cm, 30cm and 15 cm height was recorded the significant plant heights of 76.20 cm, 70.86 cm & 62.49 cm respectively. The height at which the main cotton crop was cut significantly affected the subsequent pruned cotton crops plant height, regeneration rate and the number of sprout stems per plant. Initially, the plant height of the pruned crop increased with higher cut heights. This initial growth advantage of the pruned crop could be attributed to the established root system of the pruned cotton, which facilitated water and mineral uptake, along with the availability of carbohydrates from the stump. Notably, plants pruned at greater heights and higher fertigation rates generally exhibited taller growth, consistent with earlier findings by Macharia (2013).

The dry matter production (DMP) of cotton under varying rates of NPK fertigation and different pruning techniques was analyzed (Table 1). Results indicated that both NPK fertigation and pruning techniques significantly influenced DMP in both main crop and pruned crop, whereas the interaction between NPK fertigation and pruning techniques did not show a significant effect. The DMP of crop receiving 125%, 100%, 75% and STCR was 2.21 t ha⁻¹, 2.08 t ha⁻¹, 1.73 t ha⁻¹ and 1.74 t ha⁻¹ respectively for main crop and 3.29 t ha⁻¹, 2.90 t ha⁻¹, 2.56 t ha⁻¹ and 2.60 t ha⁻¹ for pruned crop for same fertigation rates. Brar et al., 2021, who observed water and nitrogen to be among the essential growth factors as evident from better height and

biomass accumulation under their increased supply. Similar type of results was obtained by Sisodia and Khamparia (2007) and Patil (2009) and in cotton. Pruning heights of 45cm, 30cm and 15cm resulted in the values of 3.08 t ha⁻¹, 2.83 t ha⁻¹ and 2.61 t ha⁻¹ respectively, in pruned crop. Treatments interaction revealed that the DMP remained highest (3.57 t ha⁻¹) in the interaction of 125% NPK fertigation × 45cm pruning height; and it was comparable with the interaction of 125% NPK fertigation × 30cm pruning height; while the lowest DMP (3.30 t ha⁻¹) was observed in the interaction of STCR × 15cm pruning height. Primarily, both the factors such as NPK fertigation and pruning techniques had an obvious influence on DMP. The data suggest that increasing NPK fertigation rates and utilizing higher pruning heights tend to enhance dry matter production (DMP), a trend observed consistently across all NPK rates tested. Pruned cotton showed vigorous growth in terms of higher plant height, more number of leaves and branches, stem dry weight, heavier boll weight leads to increased in DMP.

Physiological parameters

The LAI of cotton (Table 1) as affected by nutrient levels and pruning techniques, and portrays that NPK fertigation levels and pruning techniques had significant influence on LAI. In main crop, LAI of crop receiving 125%, 100%, 75% and STCR based NPK fertigation was 1.69, 1.59, 1.40 and 1.42 respectively, in pruned crop 2.23, 2.06, 1.81 and 1.84 for same fertigation level. Singh *et al.* (2017) and Sankaranarayanan *et al.* (2018) observed similar results, with increase in age of crop up to 120 DAS and slowly decreased thereafter, due to ageing and senescence of leaves. The pruning heights of 15cm, 30cm and 45cm resulted in the values of 1.93, 1.99 and 2.03 respectively for this trait. Treatments interaction revealed that the LAI remained highest (1.70) in the interaction of 125% NPK fertigation × 45cm pruning height; followed by LAI 1.68 calculated in the interaction of 125% NPK fertigation × 30cm pruning height and it was on par with interaction of 125% NPK fertigation × 15 cm pruning height; while the lowest LAI (3.21) was calculated in the interaction of 75% NPK fertigation × 15cm pruning height. Primarily, both the factors such as NPK fertigation and pruning techniques had an influence on LAI. The data suggest that increasing NPK fertilizer rates and employing higher pruning heights tend to enhance leaf area index (LAI), a trend observed consistently across all tested NPK rates.

Leaf chlorophyll content in cotton was assessed using the Soil Plant Analysis Development (SPAD) chlorophyll meter (Table 2). The level of chlorophyll content in leaf is directly proportional to nitrogen content in leaf. So concentration of N in leaf strongly influences the SPAD value. The higher N also might have contributed to the formation of chlorophyll, which consequently, increased the photosynthetic activity. Study employed the impact of fertigation, pruning techniques and their interaction on the chlorophyll content remained unaffected statistically in both main crop and pruned crop. Khadar and Prakash (2014) revealed that the main crop and pruned crop maintained similar level of chlorophyll content and was not influenced by pruning heights and nutrient consortia spray. However, treatment effect showed that leaf chlorophyll content in cotton supplied with 125%, 100%, 75% and STCR was 42.07, 40.87, 38.63 and 40.21 respectively for main crop and 46.33, 44.54, 41.80 and 42.31 in pruned crop; while the crop receiving pruning techniques of 45cm, 30cm and 15 cm found to have chlorophyll content of 43.92, 43.73 and 43.58 respectively. Overall, the analysis indicated that neither fertigation levels nor pruning techniques had a statistically significant effect on leaf chlorophyll content in cotton, highlighting the robustness of chlorophyll maintenance across the tested treatments.

The absolute growth rate (AGR) of cotton was studied under various NPK fertigation levels and pruning techniques (Table 2), revealing significant effects of both NPK levels and pruning methods on AGR; while the interactive effect of NPK fertigation \times pruning techniques was found to be non-significant. The AGR of the plants receiving 125%, 100%, 75% and STCR was 3.54, 3.34, 2.81 and 2.83 g d⁻¹, respectively for main crop and 3.20 g d⁻¹, 2.74 g d⁻¹, 2.49 g d⁻¹ and 2.54 g d⁻¹ for pruned crop. Pruning techniques at heights of 45cm, 30cm and 15cm resulted in AGR values of 2.96 g d⁻¹, 2.72 g d⁻¹ and 2.55 g d⁻¹, respectively in pruned crop. Interactive effect of different factors indicated that highest AGR (3.49 g d⁻¹) was determined in crop fertilized with 125% NPK fertigation and 45cm pruning height; followed by AGR 3.20 g d⁻¹ from the interaction of 125% NPK fertigation \times 30 cm pruning height; while the least AGR (1.79 g d⁻¹) was found in the interaction of M₁ \times 15cm pruning height. The optimum NPK fertigation and pruning techniques had were the major influential elements for AGR. Even under the highest NPK level of 125% and the pruning techniques during the cotton growing season made the significant difference in the AGR. Overall, optimal NPK fertigation levels and pruning techniques were identified as significant factors influencing AGR in cotton. The data clearly

show that increasing NPK fertilizer rates and employing higher pruning heights lead to higher absolute growth rates (AGR). This trend is consistent across all tested NPK fertigation rates and pruning height, highlighting the importance of effective fertilization and pruning techniques for achieving desired crop growth in cotton.

The data in regards to CGR (Table 2) of cotton under the influence of varied rates of NPK fertigation and pruning techniques revealed that significant impact on this traits; while the combined effect of NPK fertigation x pruning techniques was non-significant. The CGR of the plants receiving 125%, 100%, 75% and STCR-based fertigation was $6.55 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, $6.18 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, $5.21 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $5.24 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, respectively for main crop and $5.93 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, $5.08 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, $4.61 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $4.71 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ for pruned crop. In pruned crops, pruning techniques of 45cm, 30cm and 15cm resulted in CGR values of $5.49 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, $5.04 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $4.72 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, respectively. Interactive effect of different factors indicated that highest CGR ($6.46 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) was determined in crop fertilized with 125% NPK fertigation and 45cm pruning height; followed by CGR $5.93 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ observed from the interaction of 125% NPK fertigation x 30 cm pruning height; while the least CGR ($4.33 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) was found in the interaction of STCR-based fertigation x 15cm pruning height. Optimal NPK fertigation and pruning techniques were identified as crucial factors influencing CGR. Increasing NPK fertigation rates corresponded with higher CGR values across all pruning levels, illustrating a positive correlation. Similarly, increasing pruning height generally enhanced CGR, consistent across all NPK rates. These findings underscore the importance of judiciously applying NPK fertigation and appropriate pruning techniques to maximize cotton crop growth. The significant progress in physiological parameters was primarily attributed to the increased availability of nutrients, continuously supplied through fertigation. This method ensured that, crop received adequate water and nutrient for its biochemical processes. The increased growth and dry matter production (DMP), resulting in higher absolute growth rate (AGR) and crop growth rate (CGR), observed in pruned cotton at higher cutting height and supplemented with 125% recommended dose of fertilizer (RDF) at 60 DAP, could be attributed to variations in leaf area, leaf number and enhanced dry matter production at this stage. Madagoudra *et al.* (2023) who observed the CGR, RGR, NAR and LAI all peaked under the treatment involving conventional tillage with higher dose of NPK, supplemented by cotton residue at 3 tons per hectare and decomposing microorganisms at 12 kilograms per hectare.

The data regards to RGR (Table 2) of cotton, influenced by varied rates of NPK fertigation and pruning techniques and their combined effect NPK fertigation x pruning techniques was found to be non-significant. The RGR values for main crop plants receiving 125%, 100%, 75% and STCR-based fertigation was $0.0734 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$, $0.0731 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$, $0.0720 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$ and $0.0704 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$, respectively and $0.0301 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$, $0.0300 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$, $0.0285 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$ and $0.0297 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$ for pruned crop; while pruning techniques of 45cm, 30cm and 15cm resulted in RGR up to $0.0300 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$, $0.0294 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$ and $0.0294 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$, respectively. The highest RGR ($0.0303 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$) occurred with 125% NPK fertigation and 45cm pruning height, followed by 125% NPK fertigation with 30cm pruning height (RGR $0.0301 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$), while the lowest RGR ($0.0280 \text{ mg g}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$) was observed with M1x15cm pruning height. These findings highlight that while NPK fertigation levels and pruning techniques individually influence RGR in cotton, their combined effect does not significantly alter RGR values.

CONCLUSION

The growth and development of both the main crop and pruned crop were significantly influenced by fertigation treatments, with pruned cotton showing notable impacts from both fertigation and pruning techniques. Fertigation at 125% NPK positively affected plant height, dry matter production, leaf area index, absolute growth rate and crop growth rate in main crop and in pruned crop 25% additional dose of N fertigation recorded higher plant height, dry matter production, leaf area index, absolute growth rate and crop growth rate. Moreover, these growth parameters reached their peak levels under the 125% NPK fertigation and 25% additional dose of N after pruning combined with pruning at a 45cm height. The research findings suggest that applying 125% NPK as drip fertigation for main crop along with pruning at a height of 45cm and 25% additional dose of N fertigation after pruning represents an optimal agronomic strategy for achieving higher seed cotton yields and improving yield traits in pruned cotton crops.

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Conflict of interest

Authors have declared that there was no conflict of interest exists.

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Table 1. Effect of drip fertigation and pruning techniques on plant height, dry matter production and leaf area index of ELS cotton CO14 (Pooled mean data of two years- winter 2021 and summer 2022)

Treatments	Plant height (cm)		DMP (t ha ⁻¹)		Leaf area index	
	Main crop	Pruned crop	Main crop	Pruned crop	Main crop	Pruned crop
Fertigation						
M ₁	60.14	67.11	1.73	2.56	1.40	1.81
M ₂	61.97	70.38	2.08	2.90	1.59	2.06
M ₃	66.85	76.30	2.21	3.29	1.69	2.23
M ₄	58.71	65.63	1.74	2.60	1.42	1.84
S.Ed.	1.25	1.17	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03
CD	NS	5.02	0.15	0.15	0.09	0.13
Pruning technique						
S ₁	-	62.49	-	2.61	-	1.93
S ₂	-	70.86	-	2.83	-	1.99
S ₃	-	76.20	-	3.08	-	2.03
S.Ed.	-	1.20	-	0.04	-	0.03
CD	-	2.42	-	0.08	-	0.06
Fertigation X Pruning technique (M at S)						
S.Ed.	-	2.00	-	0.06	-	0.05
CD	-	4.18	-	NS	-	0.10
Pruning technique X Fertigation (S at M)						
S.Ed.	-	1.70	-	0.05	-	0.04
CD	-	3.43	-	NS	-	0.08

Table 2. Effect of drip fertigation and pruning techniques on Chlorophyll content (SPAD), absolute growth rate, crop growth rate and relative growth rate of ELS cotton CO14 (Pooled mean data of two years- winter 2021 and summer 2022)

Treatments	Chlorophyll content		AGR g day ⁻¹		CGR g m ⁻² d ⁻¹		RGR mg g ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	
	Main crop	Pruned crop	Main crop	Pruned crop	Main crop	Pruned crop	Main crop	Pruned crop
Fertigation								
M ₁	38.63	41.80	2.81	2.49	5.21	4.61	0.0720	0.0285
M ₂	40.87	44.54	3.34	2.74	6.18	5.08	0.0731	0.0300
M ₃	42.07	46.33	3.54	3.20	6.55	5.93	0.0734	0.0301
M ₄	40.21	42.31	2.83	2.54	5.24	4.71	0.0704	0.0297
S.Ed.	0.69	0.80	0.06	0.05	0.11	0.09	0.00	0.00
CD	NS	NS	0.25	0.23	0.45	0.38	NS	NS
Pruning technique								
S ₁	-	43.58	-	2.55	-	4.72	-	0.0300
S ₂	-	43.73	-	2.72	-	5.04	-	0.0294
S ₃	-	43.92	-	2.96	-	5.49	-	0.0294
S.Ed.	-	0.73	-	0.05	-	0.09	-	0.00
CD	-	NS	-	0.09	-	0.19	-	NS
Fertigation X Pruning technique (M at S)								
S.Ed.	-	1.26	-	0.07	-	0.16	-	0.00
CD	-	NS	-	NS	-	NS	-	NS
Pruning technique X Fertigation (S at M)								
S.Ed.	-	1.03	-	0.06	-	0.13	-	0.00
CD	-	NS	-	NS	-	NS	-	NS